

Table 2. Effect of crop establishment methods on yield and economics of rice, 1996-97.

Treatment	Days to 50% flowering		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Net return (Rs ha ⁻¹)		Return Re ⁻¹ invested	
	Kuruvai ^a	Thaladi	Kuruvai	Thaladi	Kuruvai	Thaladi	Kuruvai	Thaladi	Kuruvai	Thaladi
Transplanting (S1)	85.9	105.4	5.9	5.0	7.2	5.5	17,542	12,813	2.40	2.02
Sowing sprouted seeds in lines manually (S2)	78.8	98.5	5.8	5.2	7.4	5.7	18,303	14,657	2.58	2.27
Drum seeding of sprouted seeds (S3)	78.9	98.7	6.0	5.3	7.4	5.7	19,453	15,046	2.75	2.30
CD (P = 0.05)	0.62	0.55	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.180	0.172

^aKuruvai = Jun-Oct, thaladi = Oct-Feb. ^bns = not significant.

requires only 9 kg of pulling force to operate. The machine weight is 11 kg without seed and 19 kg with seed (2 kg seed hopper⁻¹). It requires 14 person-h to cover 1 ha.

Direct seeding reduced the time to 50% flowering by 7 d in both the kuruvai and thaladi seasons in both years (Tables 1 and 2). The delay in flower emergence by 1 wk in transplanted rice might be due to the transplanting shock experienced by the seedlings.

The methods of crop establishment showed no significant influence on grain yield of rice in both the kuruvai and thaladi seasons in both years of study. In both seasons, however, drum seeding gave a slightly higher grain yield. A similar trend was noticed in the case of straw yield. Yield parameters such as number of panicles, panicle length, number of filled and immature grains, and 1,000-grain weight were not affected by the method of crop establishment.

Net savings averaged Rs 1,911 (US\$47) and Rs 2,233 (US\$56) ha⁻¹ in the drum-seeding method versus the transplanting method in the kuruvai and thaladi seasons, respectively. The drum-seeding method required only 8 person-h whereas line sowing of sprouted seeds and transplanting methods required 200 and 400 person-h ha⁻¹, respectively. There is thus a significant savings of labor in the drum-seeding method. ■

Optimum seedlings per unit area for high-yielding rice varieties in the hill zone of Karnataka

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Rice is the major field crop grown during monsoon under rainfed conditions in the hill zone of Karnataka (located between 11° 56' and 15° 46' north latitude and 74° 31' and 76° 4' east longitude). For improved low- and midland rice cultivation, 20 × 10-cm spacing (50 hills m⁻²) is being recommended for improved rice varieties. Adoption of this recommendation by farmers was low on the grounds that the number of seedlings recommended per m² was too high.

To verify whether the number of seedlings per unit area could be reduced, an experiment was conducted with the popular high-tillering variety

Intan during 1993 and 1994. The experiment was continued during 1995 and low-tillering, high-yielding, blast-tolerant variety DWR 4107 (Hemavati) was included. DWR 4107 has been released to replace Intan in high-blast pressure areas of the zone.

A randomized block design replicated four times was employed in 1993 and 1994. A split-plot design was employed in 1995 with varieties as main plots and plant spacing as subplots. In addition to the recommended spacing, an additional four spacings were used to produce 45, 40, 35, and 30 hills m⁻². Depending on climatic factors, nursery sowing and transplanting varied over the years. Sowing and transplanting were done in Jul 1993. Sowing was done in Jun 1994 and 1995 and transplanting was done in Jul 1994 and Aug 1995. Net plot size was 12.5 m² during 1993 and 1994 and 9.6 m² during 1995. Recommended P (33 kg P ha⁻¹) and K (72.6 kg K ha⁻¹) along with 50% N (37.5 kg N ha⁻¹) were applied at the time of

transplanting and the balance of N was topdressed in two splits at 30 and 60 d after transplanting. There was no need for plant protection measures in any of the 3 yr.

Compared with 1993 and 1995, grain yield of Intan was significantly higher in 1994 (see table) because sowing and transplanting were done on time during that year. The seedlings were not sufficiently aged in 1993 and they were overmatured in 1995 (see table). Grain yield from the recommended 50 seedlings m⁻² was significantly different from that produced by 30, 35, 40, and 45 seedlings m⁻² each year, indicating that a similar grain yield could be obtained by adopting wider spacing, accommodating as few as 30 seedlings m⁻². There were significant differences between treatments for other characters, but these differences were not reflected in grain yield.

A pooled analysis over the 3 yr indicated that there was a significant increase in tillers plant⁻¹ and panicles

Effect of number of seedlings m⁻² on rice yield and its components in the hill zone of Karnataka.^a

Variety	Year/ seedlings hill ⁻¹	Plant height (cm)	Tillers plant ⁻¹ (no.)	Panicles plant ⁻¹ (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Grains panicle ⁻¹		Panicle sterility (%)	1,000- grain weight (g)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
						Total	Chaffy			Grain	Straw
Intan	1993	102 b	9.3 b	9.2 b	21.0 b	120.5 b	22.6 b	19.0	25.3 a	4.98 b	7.50 a
	1994	104 a	10.1 a	9.9 a	21.6 a	127.2 b	21.7 b	17.1	24.5 b	6.24 a	7.92 a
	1995	100 c	7.6 c	7.6 c	21.9 a	149.0 a	27.8 a	18.5	23.5 c	4.43 c	5.72 b
	CD (5%)	0.92	0.59	0.57	0.35	7.55	3.69	ó	0.48	0.26	0.55
	30	102	10.0 a	9.8 a	21.3	135.8	25.0	18.9	24.1 b	5.12	6.96
	35	102	9.2 b	9.1 b	21.6	134.0	23.9	17.5	24.3 ab	5.09	7.08
	40	102	9.0 b	8.9 b	21.7	131.0	24.7	19.0	24.7 a	5.26	6.88
	45	102	8.7 bc	8.6 bc	21.3	126.9	24.4	19.1	24.2 ab	5.21	6.99
	50	102	8.1 c	8.1 c	21.7	133.5	22.0	16.7	24.8 a	5.39	7.31
	Mean 1993-95	102	9.0	8.9	21.5	132.2	24.0	18.2	24.4	5.21	7.05
CD (5%)	-	0.76	0.73	-	-	-	-	0.70	-	-	
CV (%)	1.40	10.17	9.93	2.54	8.90	23.94	22.01	3.09	7.81	12.09	
DWR4107	1995	106	7.2 a	7.2 a	22.9 ab	159.3	11.9 ab	7.3 ab	21.1	2.96	4.46
	30	105	6.8 b	7.0 ab	22.1 ab	159.0	13.4 a	8.4 a	20.5	3.11	4.69
	35	106	6.6 b	6.6 bc	23.1 a	166.5	13.1 a	7.7 ab	21.6	3.28	4.40
	40	106	6.1 c	6.1 c	22.0 ab	144.2	9.2 b	6.7 ab	20.7	3.18	4.53
	45	106	6.0 c	6.0 c	21.9 b	146.3	9.3 b	6.1 b	21.1	3.23	4.67
	50	105	6.0 c	6.0 c	22.4	135.0	11.4	7.3	21.0	3.15	4.55
	Mean	106	6.5	6.6	22.4	135.0	11.4	7.3	21.0	3.15	4.55
	CD (5%)	-	0.44	0.61	1.20	-	3.56	2.12	-	-	-
	CV (%)	1.91	4.34	6.00	3.47	10.91	20.26	18.90	3.76	6.98	12.83
	Intan	1995	100	7.6 a	7.6	21.9	149.0 b	27.8 a	18.5 a	23.5 a	4.43 a
DWR4107	1995	106	6.5 b	6.6	22.4	135.0 a	11.4 b	7.3 b	21.0 b	3.15 b	4.55
Mean	103	7.1	7.1	22.4	152.0	19.6	12.9	22.3	3.79	5.13	
CD (5%)	-	0.81	-	-	3.72	15.34	11.17	2.28	0.58	-	
CV (%)	1.78	7.46	7.9	3.40	10.38	31.63	27.98	3.34	11.32	14.47	

^aMean values followed by dissimilar letters are significantly different from one another.

plant⁻¹ and a significant decrease in grain weight in the treatment with wider spacing (30 hills m⁻²) compared with the treatment with narrow spacing (50 hills m⁻²) and these traits were similar in treatments with 35, 40, and 45 hills m⁻². But grain and straw yield were statistically similar in all the

treatments. Thus, wider spacing between hills as a result of higher tillering compensates for reduced hills and grain yield will be on a par with narrow spacing, which requires 20 seedlings more per m². The data obtained with DWR 4107 also confirmed the same trend (see figure).

The results obtained with two varieties significantly different from each other for tillering ability revealed that grain and straw yield with recommended spacing of 50 hills m⁻² was on a par with spacings for 30-45 hills m⁻². We therefore suggest revising the number of seedlings recommended per m² and reducing it by 20.

Intan was significantly superior to DWR4107 in tillering, grain yield, and grain weight, though it showed significantly higher chaffy grains panicle⁻¹ and panicle sterility. The significantly lower grain yield of DWR4107 is attributed to aged seedlings. ■

Influence of plant population on grain yield of rice.

Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.